

**MANAGEMENT OF SIDHMA KUSHTA THROUGH VAMANA KARMA-
A SINGLE CASE STUDY****Dr. Chaitra^{1*}, Dr. Pallavi M.²**

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ABSTRACT

Skin is the largest organ in the human body, act as a robust barrier against external threats and plays a crucial role in various inflammatory process, including immune responses to infections, autoimmune reactions and allergies. Skin is a shield which protects us from various external invasions. In Ayurveda, any disease impacting the skin is categorized under the term Kushta and has pointed at its multi-factorial etiology. Diet, behaviour, environment, genetics and immunologic factors all appear to have role in the development of Kushta Roga. Based on the Amsamsavikalpa of Dosha- Dushya, Kushta is mainly divided into two groups Mahakushta and Ekakushta. Among these, SidhmaKushta is a MahaKushta. A 21 year old female Patient complains of Coppery White Patches over the Chest and Back of the Whole Body associated with Itching and Burning Sensation. The disease diagnosed as Sidhma Kushta underwent Classical Ayurvedic treatments such

as Vamana Karma i.e Shodana Chikitsa and Shamana Chikitsa. They can be prevented by following proper diet and lifestyle mentioned in Ayurveda.

KEYWORDS: Vamana Karma, Sidhma Kushta, Shodana Karma.**INTRODUCTION**

Skin is the seat of complexion which depends on factors like nutrition, hygiene, circulation, age, immunity, genetic traits and mental state. Twak Vikara Nidanas are most typically arises

due to Mithyaahara, Vihara, Manasika Nidana, vitiates the Tridosha which further leads to affliction and aggravation of Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa and Lasika.^[1] Kushta is divided into two types based on Severity i.e Mahakushta and Kshudrakushta.^[2] SidhmaKushta is described under Mahakushta.^[3] Sidhma Kushta is included into Vatakaphaja type of Kushta. KushtaRoga is included in Ashta Mahagadas by Acharyas due to its difficulty in management for the cure of Kushta Roga, A judicious blend of Shodhana Karma and Shamana Karma are needed with Proper Pathya Ahara and Vihara to prevent its relapse. Patient of Kushta should be administered with Vamana Karma every fortnight.^[5] So, accordingly Vamana Karma was administered following the Classical Methodology, Patient diagnosis was done initially along with Dashavidha and Asthavidha Pariksha. Patient was in Samavashta, Pachana was given for achieving the Niramavastha. So, this Case is managed with Shodana Chikitsa i.e Vamana Karma and Shamana Karma.

CASE REPORT

HISTORY OF PRESENT ILLNESS

A female patient aged 21 years old, N/K/C/O DM and HTN was apparently normal a year ago. Then Patient complains of small Coppery White Patches over the Chest and Back of the Whole body associated with Itching and Burning sensation. For all these complaints Patient visited our hospital for better management.

PAST HISTORY

No significant suffering or any surgical intervention was obtained in past history which could contribute the pathology.

PERSONAL HISTORY

Bowel - Not Clear (Once in two days)

Appetite - Good **Micturition** - Normal **Sleep** - Disturbed

Diet - Food habits such as Tea, Chapati, Rice, Dal, Chicken, Bhaji, Biscuits, Sweets, Junkfood, Cool drinks etc.

FAMILY HISTORY

Nothing significant.

NIDANA PANCHAKA

Hetu - Ahara – Guru, Sheeta, Atiushna Ahara Vihara - Divaswapa, Ratrijagarana.

PURVARUPA

Discolouration and appearance of rashes on the skin associated with Itching and Piercing Pain, Tingling sensation and Physical exhaustion.

RUPA

Appearance of small Coppery White patches present on the Chest, Back of Whole body along with Itching and Burning sensation.

UPASHAYA**SHAMANA AUSHADI**

Manjishtadi Kashya 3tsp BD/BF Cap. Tiktamrut 1BD/AF Evenshade Cream E/A

Duration – 1 month

SAMPRAPTI^[5]

Due to Hetusevana, Tridosha Prakopa, Shaithilya Utpati, Twacha, Rakta, Mamsa, Sharirstha Jaliya Dhatu (Lasika) Dushti, Kledotpatti takes place, Shweta, Tamra Varnayukta Vaivarnya, Daha, Kandu takes place leading to Sidhma Kushta.

GENERAL EXAMINATION

Pallor - Absent Icterus - Absent Clubbing - Absent

Cyanosis - Absent

Lymphadenopathy – Absent Edema – Absent

Bp – 110/70 Mm/Hg Pulse – 70bpm

SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION

CVS – S1, S2 heard, no murmurs

RS – Normal Vesicular Breathing heard, no added sounds GIT – Soft, non-tender

CNS – Conscious, oriented

INTEGUMENTARY EXAMINATION

Site of lesion - Chest, Back of the Whole body Shape - Circular with irregular boundaries
Size - Smaller to little bigger one.

Color - Coppery white, Touch- Rough, dry, hard.

MANAGEMENT

1. Deepana and Pachana with Chitrakadi Vati – 7 days.

- Consent for Vamana Karma was taken.
- Vamana Karma (Shodana Chikitsa) :- It is divided into Purvakarma, Pradhana Karma and Paschat Karma.

PURVAKARMA - Patient was prepared for Snehapana with Mahatiktaka Ghrita. Samyak Snigdha lakshanas^[6] were obtained in four days as Patient was Madhyama Koshta.

Snehapana Lakshanas were as follows.

Table no. 1: Snehapana Chart.

Snehapan a day	Date	Dose	Time of Snehapana	Time of Shudda Ugara	Jaranakaala	Lakshanas
1 st day	20/3/24	30 ml	7:45 am	12:45 pm	5hrs	-
2 nd day	21/3/24	75ml	7:50 am	1:50 pm	6hrs	Shirashoola Klama, Sada
3 rd day	22/3/24	120ml	7:35 am	2:35 pm	7hrs	Asamhata Varchas
4 th day	23/3/24	180ml	7:40 am	3:00 pm	7hrs 20mins	Twak Snigdha, Snigdha Varchas

Diet in Snehapana kala – Drava, Ushna, Anabhishtyandi Ahara.

Vishrama kala – 1 day (24/3/24)

Management in Vishramakala

- Sarvanga Abhyanga with Nalpamardi taila
- Sarvanga Parisheka with Nimba Patra

Diet in Vishramakala – Kaphavridhikara Aharas such as Dahi Vada with Curd, Curd with Sugar, Curd Rice, Bananas, Sweets etc.

PRADHANA KARMA – On the day of Vamana (25/3/24)

Patient was asked for morning natural urges (Urine and Stool) and after that

- Sarvanga Abhyanga with Nalpamardi taila
- Sarvanga Parisheka with Nimba Patra was done.

After that 2 litres of Ksheera was given to patient for Akantapana. Vamaka yoga was given to patient after akantapana which was as follows.

Vamaka yoga

Madanaphala PippaliChurna - 4.5 grams Vacha Churna – 2 grams

Saindhava Lavana – 1 gram Honey – Q.S.

Vamanopaga Dravya - Yashtimadhu Phanta

Sweda Pradurbhava, Romaharsha, KukshiAdhamana and Hrullasa^[7], was observed after 48 minutes of consuming Vamaka Yoga. Vamanopaga Dravya i.e Yashtimadhuphanta was given for easy Vamana Procedure. Vitals i.e Pulse rate and Blood Pressure was checked throught the Vamana Procedure.

Table No. 2: Vamana Chart.

Time	Consumed dravya	Quantity	Vega	Symptoms	Vitals
7:15 am	Ksheera	2 litres	1 Vega	-	Bp- 110/70 mm/hg Pulse –72bpm
7: 25 am	Vamana Yoga	7.5 grams		Sweda Pravrutti, Hrullasa, Kukshi adhmana, Ksheera pravartana	Bp- 100/70 mm/hg Pulse –69 bpm
8:05 am	Yashtimadhu Phanta	4 litres	6Vega	Aushadi Pravartana, Katu-TiktaAsyata and Pitta Pravartana, Shirashoola	Bp- 130/90 mm/hg Pulse –70bpm
8:40 am	Saindhava jala	1 litre	1 Vega	Katu-tikta Asyata reduced, Udara Laghuta	Bp- 120/90 mm/hg Pulse –78bpm
8:50 am	-	-	-	Shareera laghuta and Indriya Prasannata	Bp- 120/80 mm/hg Pulse –77bpm
Total		7 litre	6 litre	-	-

Consumed Dravya – 7 litre Vomited Dravya – 6litre Vega – 8 Vega

Type of Shuddhi – Pravara^[8] Antiki Shuddhi – Pittanta

Lainghiki Shuddhi – Shareeralaghavata, Indriya Prasannata, Hridaya and Parshwa Shuddhi and Shiro laghuta.^[9]

PASCHAT KARMA

After completion of Vamana procedure, Patient was asked to clean the mouth, face, hand and feet with warm water and asked to take rest. After that Dhoomapana was done, Samsarjana Krama of 7 days was given to Patient and told about Pariharya Vishayas.

Table No. 3: Samsarjana Krama^[10] Chart.

DAY	ANNAKALA	AHARA
1 st	Evening	Peya
2 nd	Morning	Peya
	Evening	Peya
3 rd	Morning	Vilepi
	Evening	Vilepi
4 th	Morning	Vilepi
	Evening	Akrita Yusha
5 th	Morning	Krita Yusha
	Evening	Krita Yusha
6 th	Morning	Akrita Mamsarasa
	Evening	Krita Mamsarasa
7 th	Morning	Krita Mamsarasa
	Evening	Normal diet

After completion of Samsarjana Krama, Shamana Chikitsa was given to Patient for 1 month.

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

“Fig.1” Before treatment.

“Fig.2” After treatment.

Table No. 4: Treatment Outcome.

Features	Before treatment	After treatment
Itching	Severe	Absent
Patches	Severe	Mild
Burning sensation	Severe	Absent
Sleep	Disturbed	Sound

DISCUSSION

The management protocols for Kustha, as it is considered a Kleda Pradoshaja Vyadhi

involving the Sapta Dravya Sangraha in its development. In this case, it is a Vata Kapha Pradhana Kushta. The predominance of Vata dosha causes Pain, dryness and the predominance of Kapha dosha causes Burning sensation, Itching etc., In Kushta Roga, Viruddha Aharadi Nidana vitiate Tridosha and cause Dushya of Twak, Rakta, Mamsa and Ambu. In the Samprapti of Kustha, Rasa Raktadushti places an important role. The disease manifested in the skin in this case, the lesions were seen in Chest and Back of Whole body as around coppery white coloured rough patches. The symptoms most closely resemble Sidhma Kushta in which Patches seems like smooth inner side surrounded by a dry part.

The initial treatment done were aimed at correcting the Agni, Chitrakadi Vati was given along with strict dietary control helped to alleviate the symptoms. Snehapana was done with Mahatikthaka Ghrita. Then it was followed by Vamana Karma. As there is involvement of Kapha dosha, due to the Ashraya Ashrayee Bhava, it vitiates Kleda. Kledata is arised due to the Snighdhata, Slakshna Guna of Kapha and it can be eliminated by Vamana Karma.

This facilitates the monitoring of the frequency of disease recurrence and its potential for further spread. Proper Patya Ahara Viharas were followed during the treatment time to get maximum result and to prevent complications due to Apathyaacharana. A wholesome diet will make a suitable substratum for the medicine to act in the body.

CONCLUSION

Ayurvedic treatment of Sidhma Kustha offers a holistic and time-tested approach, addressing not just the symptoms but the root cause of the disease. By balancing the Tridosha and focusing on detoxification, rejuvenation and strengthening of the immune system.

Ayurveda ensures long-term relief and overall well-being. Traditional therapies like Vamana Karma, One among the Panchakarma, along with the administration of herbal formulations plays a crucial role in purifying the blood and nourishing the skin.

Moreover, lifestyle modifications and a disciplined dietary regimen are integral parts of Ayurvedic treatment, helping to prevent the recurrence of Sidhma Kustha. Practices like Yoga, Meditation, and Pranayama further support the healing process by reducing stress and promoting harmony within the body and mind. Thus, Ayurvedic management of Sidhma Kustha stands as a comprehensive and effective strategy, embracing natural remedies and mindful practices to restore skin health and enhance the quality of life in a sustainable and

balanced way. Also remission in signs and symptoms of patient was observed after treatment. It can be concluded that Vamana Karma (Shodhana Chikitsa) and Shamana chikitsa is significantly effective in treatment of Sidhma Kushtha. Kushtha is difficult to cure hence prolong treatment in the form of Shodhana and Shamana is needed to avoid recurrence of disease.

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